

MEDICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEMS OF HEALTH PRESERVATION OF STUDENTS

¹Sharipova D.D., ²Tairova M.

^{1,2}Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14563170>

Abstract. *It is important to suggest that one of the actual areas of social policy in Uzbekistan is the preservation and strengthening of students' health at all stages of the continuous education system. This idea was transformed into a plan for the most important scientific research of Uzbek Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences named after Kary-Niyazi, which was implemented starting in the 60s by the sector of physical education, age physiology and hygiene, divided in 1970 into the laboratory of age physiology and hygiene of children and adolescents, as well as the laboratory of physical education.*

Keywords: *school hygiene, age physiology, energy metabolism, defectology.*

By this time, scientific contacts had been established between the above-mentioned sector and the Institute of Age Physiology and School Hygiene of the USSR Academy of Pedagogical Sciences, and intensive work was underway to train scientific personnel and returned to Tashkent to the UzAPS as candidates of biological sciences, T.S.Usmankhodjaev, A. Agzamov, K. Makamjanov, M. Tashpulatov, who conducted research on the health-improving focus of physical education of students in comprehensive schools. Education reforms in the 1970s required increased attention to the health of children and adolescents studying under new educational programs. In this regard, research conducted in the laboratory of age physiology and hygiene of children and adolescents was included in the plan of the most important studies of the Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of the USSR, and the study of the problem of adaptation of students to educational and physical activity in the climatic conditions of Uzbekistan during the next 3 five-year plans was included in the number of co-executors (and Uzbekistan was the only one of the Central Asian republics) of all-Union complex studies coordinated by the Institute of Age Physiology and Hygiene of the Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of the USSR.

Besides that, in order to ensure the relationship between theoretical developments and practice, an experimental laboratory for conducting physiological and hygienic research in a natural experiment began to function at School N. 115 in Shaykhantakhur district in Tashkent. The laboratory was equipped with modern equipment for studying energy metabolism, the activity of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, and also using modern methods for studying the attention of students, mental and physical performance of students during academic and physical activity. The activities of our laboratory were introduced to the activities of the Vice-President of the Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of the USSR, Academician A.G. Khripkova and the famous hygienist, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor Antropova in the late 70s. Later, A.G. Khripkova, while making a speech at a meeting of the Presidium of the Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of the USSR, noted that she had the pleasure of getting acquainted with the activities of UzAPS on health preservation issues and the laboratory of the institute, which meets modern requirements and, in her opinion, is the only one of the union republics conducting research on topical issues of preserving the health of the younger generation. Systematic and targeted implementation of scientific research contributed to the fact that from among the laboratory staff and applicants of

the institute, candidate dissertations were prepared and defended under the supervision of D.D. Sharipova by K. KadIrov, S. Irgashkhodjaev, L. Simenova, K. Nurmukhamedov, A. Akbarov, E. Saitkhalilov, M. Tairova, G. Adilova, A. Arifbaev, E.S. Alibaev, F. Gulyamova, G. Sadykova, S. Azizov, K. Khaidarov, F. Yuldashev, T. Ummatkulov, A. Issimova, which allows us to talk about the creation in the Republic of a scientific school on age physiology, hygiene of education and upbringing, health-preserving pedagogy, and the formation of a healthy lifestyle.

It should be suggested that the dissertations of employees and applicants developed the scientific foundations of hygiene education, the methodological foundations of developing a healthy lifestyle, health-saving technologies, teaching children and adolescents to communicate with the public on issues of physical education and sports, and others. In October 1980, the laboratory was transformed into the Department of Physiology and Defectology, whose employees continued research on health preservation of students and correction of deviations in children with special health needs.

Since December 1986, D.D. Sharipova was transferred to the position of Deputy Director for Science at UzAPS and supervised scientific areas of psychology, pedagogy and defectology in the context of their health-preserving activities and actively worked to popularize the results of research in medical-biological and psychological-pedagogical areas aimed at raising a harmoniously developed healthy personality. It should be noted that in the 80-90s, the monographs by employees were published on health preservation issues.

Conclusion

The health preservation of students is a multifaceted issue that encompasses both medical and pedagogical challenges. The increasing prevalence of physical and mental health issues among students necessitates a comprehensive approach to promote well-being in educational settings.

1. “Holistic Health Education”: Incorporating health education into the curriculum can empower students with knowledge about healthy lifestyles, stress management, and mental health awareness.

2. “Supportive Environment”: Schools should foster an environment that prioritizes physical and mental health. This includes access to counseling services, physical activity programs, and nutritious food options.

3. “Collaboration”: Effective collaboration among educators, healthcare professionals, and families is crucial. This partnership can enhance support systems and ensure that students receive the care they need.

4. “Preventive Measures”: Implementing preventive health measures, such as regular health screenings and vaccination programs, can help identify and address health issues early.

5. “Policy and Research”: Continued research into the health challenges faced by students is essential. Policymakers should use this data to develop targeted interventions and allocate resources effectively.

By addressing these medical and pedagogical problems holistically, we can significantly improve the health and overall well-being of students, leading to better academic performance and healthier future generations.

REFERENCES

1. Sharipova D., Khamraev M., Poluyanovna R., et al. "Physical education of schoolchildren" Section of the monograph "Theory and practice of communist education of students" Fan, T., 1983.
2. Sharipova D., Semenova L. "Hygienic education and training of students". T., 1983.
3. Sharipova D., Khamraev M., Poluyanovna R., et al. "Moral aspects of sex education of schoolchildren" In the book: "Moral education of schoolchildren". T., 1984.
4. Sharipova D., Semenova L. Hygienic education and training of schoolchildren. T., 1984.
5. Sharipova D., Tairova M., Seytkhalilova E. Energy metabolism and external respiration of children and adolescents during muscular activity in hot climates. Science, T., 1985.
6. Sharipova D., Kuznetsova D. Smoking and its effects on the body. Science, T., 1992.
7. Sharipova D., et al. Social and pedagogical concept of personality formation. Science. T., 1992.

As well as a number of educational and methodological manuals:

8. Sharipova D., Semenova L. Sanitary initiation in preschool institutions. T., Medicine, 1976.
9. Sharipova D., Semenova L. Forms and methods of kindergarten work on promoting medical and pedagogical knowledge of parents. T., Medicine, 1979.
10. Sharipova D., Khamraev M., Semenova L. Promotion of hygienic knowledge among parents (to help the lecturer). T. Knowledge, 1981.
11. Sharipova D., Khamraev M., Semenova L. "Oila bilan hamkorlikda" (Together with the family) (preparing children for work, for life in the Uzbek language). T., Knowledge, 1981.
12. Sharipova D., Seytkhalilova E. Planning an annual training cycle for young handball players at the stage of preliminary preparation. T., 1981
13. Sharipova D., Kuznetsova T. Physiological criteria for dosing loads in physical education lessons in a comprehensive school (method, recommendation for school doctors and physical education teachers). T., 1982.
14. Sharipova D., Semenova L. Take care of your health from a young age. T., Medicine, 1982.
15. Sharipova D., Semenova L. Daily routine is the key to schoolchildren's health. T., Medicine, 1982.
16. Sharipova D. Improving parents' hygienic knowledge. T., Medicine, 1982.
17. Sharipova D. Schoolchildren's health protection. T., Medicine, 1984.
18. Sharipova D. Parents' hygienic knowledge. Lecture text, Knowledge, 1984.
19. Sharipova D., Semenova L. Healthy lifestyle of sanitation and hygiene regimens. T., 1984.
20. Sharipova D. Age-related features of adaptive reactions of external respiration and gas-energy metabolism of schoolchildren in hot climates. Methodical recommendations. T., UzAPS, 1984.
21. Sharipova D., Akbarov A. Improving the physical performance of the body. Methodical ability. T., TSPU named after Nizami, 1992.
22. Sharipova D., Tokareva V. Youth without smoking. Method manual. T., 2000.
23. Sharipova D. Methodical instructions on school hygiene for independent work of students. T., UzAPS, 1984.
24. Sharipova D., Semenova L. Education of correct posture. T. Medicine, 1985.
25. Sharipova D., Artikov M. Methodical recommendations for conducting biology lessons on hygiene issues in senior grades of comprehensive schools. T. Medicine, 1985.

26. Sharipova D. Methodical recommendations for conducting biology lessons. T., Medicine, 1985.
27. Sharipova D. Hygienic training and education of primary school students. T., Medicine, 1986.
28. Sharipova D. Prevention of overfatigue in schoolchildren. T., Medicine, 1986.
29. Sharipova D. Hygienic training and education in a reformed school (methodological recommendations). T., UzAPS, 1987.
30. Sharipova D., Kuznetsova T. "The foundation of health is laid in school. T., 1985.
31. Sharipova D., Chernikov V. Prevention of drug addiction and toxicomania among schoolchildren. T., 1988.
32. Sharipova D. Organization of hygiene education in the process of extracurricular and out-of-school work. Methodological recommendations. T., 1988.